

2nd All-Island Cancer Data Forum

26th and 27th January 2026, Riddell Hall, Queen's University Belfast

The Island of Ireland as a Digital Powerhouse for cancer data; How do we make it happen?

Theme: Accelerating Cancer Data Infrastructure for European Health Data Space and Health Data Research Service Readiness

Day One, Monday 26th January 2026

09.30- **Registration and Coffee**
10.00 (Riddell Room)

Session 1: Recognising the Health and Societal Dividend of Data

Chairs: Professor Mark Lawler and Professor Aedin Culhane

10.00- **Professor Ian Bruce**, Pro-Vice-Chancellor, Faculty of Medicine, Health and Life Sciences, Queen's University Belfast
10.05
Welcome and Opening Remarks

10.05- **Professor Mark Lawler**, Professor of Digital Health, Queen's University Belfast & Co-Lead All-Island ehealth-Hub for Cancer
10.25
"Data trump opinion...every time"

10.25- **Margaret Grayson**, Patient Advocate, Northern Ireland Cancer Research Consumer Forum (NICRCF)
10.35
"Use Our Data"

10.35- **Professor Aedin Culhane**, Professor of Cancer Genomics, University of Limerick & Co-Lead All-Island ehealth-Hub for Cancer
10.55
"From Fragmented Data Silos to Actionable Evidence for Care- How do we get there?"

10.55- Q & A
11.15

11.15- **Coffee & Networking**
11.45 (Isdell Courtyard)

Session 2: Connecting Data: Delivering Real World Impact

Chairs: Assoc Prof Patrick Redmond, Dr Ethna McFerran

11.45- **Luke Readman**, Director of Digital Transformation, NHS England, London
12.05
"OneLondon - Past, Present and Future"

12.05- **Professor Eva Morris**, Professor of Health Data Epidemiology, University of Oxford
12.25
"Realising the potential of big data in cancer care: challenges and opportunities in the National Health Service"

12.25- **Professor Geoff Hall**, Professor of Digital Health, University of Leeds
12.45
"How can real-world evidence studies in cancer enhance clinical trials?"

12.45- **Panel Discussion – Creating a Connected Data Ecosystem**
13.05

13.05- **Lunch and Poster Viewing**
14.00 (Isdell Courtyard)

Ministerial Address

14.00- Welcome and Introduction of Minister,
14.05 Professor Mark Lawler
14.05- Ministerial Address
14.15 **Minister Mike Nesbitt** (in person)
14.15- Closing Remarks, Thanks, and Photo
14.20 Opportunity

Session 3A Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (ODHSI) Workshop (Parallel Session)

14.30- **Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (ODHSI) Workshop**
17:30
Foundations in OMOP and Real-World Data: How to Run Your First Real-World Study

Dr Stelios Theophanous, University of Leeds
Professor Geoff Hall, University of Leeds
Dr Catherine Mahoney, Eli Lilly

Session 3B Chatham House Roundtable (Closed session)

- 14.35-17.30** The Island of Ireland as a Digital Powerhouse for cancer data; How do we make it happen?
Chatham House sessions are limited to invited participants only.
- 14.35-14.50** **Welcome & Purpose**
Mike Farrar and Mark Lawler
- 14:50 – 15:50** **Parallel Breakouts Groups**
Group A: Strategic Vision & System Leadership for cancer data research and innovation – an all-island prerogative
Group B: Cross-border cancer data research and innovation opportunities connecting NI to the Federation of European Cancer Data Node
Group C: Accelerating All Island Cancer Data Infrastructure to impact and empower patients
- 15.50 - 16.10** **Coffee Break**
- 16:10 – 17:10** **Plenary Feedback & Discussion**
- 17:10 – 17:30** **Next Steps:** Summarise actions
- 17:30** **Close session**

Day Two, Tuesday 27th January 2026

- 09.00-09:30** **Registration and Coffee**
(Riddell Room)

Session 4: The value of connecting Health Data: Realising the Benefits for Research

Chair: Dr Shirin Moghaddam

- 9.30-9.55** **Professor Dani Prieto Alhambra**, Professor of Pharmaco and Device Epidemiology, University of Oxford
“OMOP-based oncology research: from EHDEN to OPTIMA and GREG”
- 9.55-10.10** **Dr Frances Burns**, Lead for Northern Ireland Trusted Research Environment (NITRE) at HSC Data Institute

“The Northern Ireland Trusted Research Environment – an unrivalled opportunity for cancer research and innovation”

- 10.10-10.25** **Dr Christian Cole**, Reader in Health Informatics, University of Dundee
“Building Trusted Research Infrastructure in the UK”
- 10.25-10.35** **Abhishek Nayak**, eHealth-Hub, University of Limerick
“Advancing Federated sharing of Cancer Clinical and Genomic Data Across Europe”
- 10.35-11.00** **Panel Discussion** - *An ecosystem for cancer data research and innovation on the island of Ireland*

- 11.00-11.30** **Coffee & Networking]**
(Isdell Courtyard)

Session 5: Conroy-Hastings Memorial Session: Delivering for patients – we want our data!

Chairs: Aidan McCormick, Siobhan Gaynor

- 11.30-11.45** **Miriam Staunton**, Chairperson, UCAN Ireland
“The importance of advocacy in shaping evidence, policy, and access pathways”
- 11:45-12.00** **Dr Katie Crowley**, Associate Professor of Computer Science, University of Limerick
“Designing EHDS-Ready Patient Portals for Trust, Accessibility and Empowerment in Cancer Care”
- 12:00-12:15** **Caitriona Wray**, Assistant Principal Officer, Health Information Policy Unit
“Health at our fingertips through digital public service delivery”
- 12:15-12:30** **Amy Nolan**, Director of Clinical Affairs', The Irish Cancer Society
“Improving Patient Outcomes via Data Utilisation”
- 12.30-12:45** **Professor Michael Quinn**, Professor of Practice, Queens University Belfast

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"Encompass – a digital transformation but it's only the start!"

12:45-13:05 **Professor Ruth Clifford**, Consultant Hematologist, University Hospital Limerick

"Connecting Blood Cancer Data to Improve Patient Outcomes"

13:05 - 13:20 **Panel Discussion**
Connecting the dots: patients, data and delivery

13:20-14:15 **Lunch and Poster Viewing (Isdell Courtyard)**

Session 6: Delivering precision cancer medicine

Chairs: Kathryn McGinnis, Lara Edwards

14:15-14:35 **Dr. Joep de Ligt**, Data Lead, Hartwig Medical Foundation, Netherlands

"Cancer Genomics in the Netherlands; Predicting non-response and the Implementation of OMOP"

14:35-14:55 **Professor Richard Kennedy**, Global Vice President, Biomarker Development and Medical Director, Almac Diagnostic Services
"Precision Oncology: What's the reality?"

14:55-15:10 **Brendan Reardon**, Dana Farber Cancer Institute and University of Limerick
"Towards an All-Island Precision Oncology Knowledge Base"

15:10-15:25 **Sarah Hersey**, Vice President Precision Medicine, Bristol Myers Squibb
"Precision Medicine: What's so difficult?"

15:25-15:50 **Panel Discussion** - Precision Oncology – An All-Island opportunity?

15:50-16:00 Closing remarks

eHealth-Hub for Cancer

This meeting is hosted by the All-Island eHealth Hub for Cancer, <https://www.ehealth4cancer.ie/> an €4M Emerging Hub of Excellence funded under the Shared Island Fund, through the Irish Higher Education Authority's North South Research Programme. It is co-led by Professor Mark Lawler, Professor of Digital Health and Chair in Translational Cancer Genomic at the Johnston Cancer Research Centre at Queen's University Belfast and Professor Aedin Culhane, Full Professor of Cancer Genomics, and Director Limerick Digital Cancer Research Centre. The goal of the eHealth Hub is to develop data standards and frameworks to connect cancer data and enable federated cancer data research, and to deliver research and innovation with impact on the island of Ireland. **Contact:** eHealth@ul.ie

Reports

- [Harnessing the Power of Data to Transform Cancer Research, Care and Innovation Across the Island of Ireland](#) Lawler M, Culhane A, Heenan D, Keatley D, Bennett D, Gaynor S, Lowery M, McCabe S, 2025
- [All-Island Cancer Research Landscape Report \(2019-2024\)](#) Shashank Srinivas, Anisa Shah, Mark Lawler and William M. Gallagher (2025)
- [Landscape Review and Economic Potential of the Oncology and Allied Digital Health Sector on the Island of Ireland](#) Henderson R., O'Flatharta N., Patterson K., and Redmond S (2024)

1+MG Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI)

Ireland's GDI (<https://genomicdata.ie/>) serves as the national node for the EU 1+Million Genomes initiative, creating a secure platform for sharing and analyzing genomic data

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OHDSI-Ireland All-Island Node

Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI, pronounced "Odyssey"), is a global open-science collaborative transforming healthcare evidence through large-scale analytics of observational real-world health data. Over 140 different medical coding systems (eg SNOMED, ICD-10, etc) are mapped to the common data format called OMOP, permitting simpler, faster and standardized research across sites. Importantly sensitive patient data never moves, instead researchers send analysis code to each data sites. It is a federated network of data partners; each retains control of their own data. Only summarized or aggregated results are returned. The OHDSI-Ireland All-Island Node <https://www.ohdsi-europe.org/index.php/national-nodes/ireland> meets monthly, host training seminars and discussions.

CANDLE National Cancer Data Nodes

National Cancer Data Nodes are country-level hubs that will securely manage and share cancer patient data for research and care, without moving sensitive information. They're aligned with the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and are part of Europe's plan to fight cancer faster by linking hospitals, researchers, and registries across borders. CANDLE (National CANcer data Node DeveLopErs) is funded EU Horizon Europe (2025-2028) program (<https://candle-project.eu/>) to help countries build an NCDN, and align with EHDS rules.

European Health Data Space (EHDS)

A legally mandated EU regulation (2025/327) creating a secure cross-border EU network for sharing electronic health data. In 2029, patients gain access to their health records (via an app) while researchers and policy-makers can be approved for access (by the Health Data Access Body) to anonymized real world health data for secondary analysis. EHDS operates decentrally: each EU country will establish its own infrastructure and controls its national data. Cancer NCDN will be the first domain-specific instance of the EHDS.

- o EHDS patient data access (Ireland) MyHealth@EU, myHealth@myHands :myH: <https://www.ehealthireland.ie/>
- o EHDS research (secondary use) HealthData@EU <https://www.hiqa.ie/areas-we-work/health-information/healthdataie>

HDR UK

Health Data Research UK (HDR UK) serves as the UK's national institute for health data science, uniting NHS, academic, and industry datasets to drive discoveries in disease prevention and treatment.

<https://healthdatagateway.org/en>

Health Data Research Service (HDRS)

The Health Data Research Service (HDRS) is a UK government-backed national platform announced in 2025 designed to streamline secure access to linked health data for approved researchers. It creates a single "front door" to trusted research environments (TREs), cutting approval times from months to weeks while upholding privacy and oversight.

DATA-CAN

DATA-CAN is the UK's HDR Hub for cancer. It links NHS cancer records, genomic data, and research cohorts into secure environments, enabling researchers to analyze patient data without moving raw data. See Table 1 for listing of NI Health and Cancer data organizations.